

Parsing Metadata from Natural Language: A Case in Embedded Software Development

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ABSTRACT In the manufacturing industry, especially in high-tech fields. The application of distributed data collection and tracking support systems is extremely important, especially in the field of automated production where machines must operate 24/7 and the management of production systems is very important. Automated production effectively becomes a competitive advantage for enterprises because it greatly affects production efficiency, product quality, and other operational indicators. Integrated embedded development process is the design and construction process in which system engineering application, software development process, testing process and fuzzy set data mining are established. The article provides an automated system solution for tracking sewing parameters in production, applying programming language models and wired networks to build a processing system and collect analytical data. Research results are still being implemented and are recommended by the team for application on the ABC company's global network.

KEYWORDS Data Processing; Fuzzy Matching; System Engineering.

I. INTRODUCTION

AUTOMATION in production has become a development field for a long time, where the production role of machines is put on top and the appearance of humans is largely in several stages such as monitoring and control, control, maintenance, assemblies, and outsourcing... The replacement of automation in related processes is inevitable, including machine data tracking, and editing processes.

Most industrial machines are designed and manufactured by third parties, based on the requirements of the investor (parent company), so programming and control software is developed by stakeholders. The units that understand the structure and principles work together with the software development department to produce a tool that the customer (investment company) can use in the operational area. And used in a common environment to connect and manage systems, that is SCADA, now there are many other methods can be expanded, for example, supporting PC with PLC in

monitoring and connecting server, supporting control ports and discrete sensors...

A SCADA network typically includes a control server placed at the control center, communication links and one or more topographically dispersed field sites containing field devices. The SCADA sensors and actuators at field sites monitor the different attributes of electromechanical equipment continuously and send signals to field control devices like Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), Remote Terminal Unit (RTU) or Intelligent Electronic Device (IED). Via communication links, the transfer of information transpires back and forth between field control devices and the control center. The field control devices will supply digital status information to the control center, where software will process the status information and determine acceptable parameter ranges. This information will then be transmitted to the field device(s) where action may be taken in order to avoid various hazards or optimize the performance of the

system. The control center will store the status information in data historian and display it on a HMI (Human Machine Interface) which provides centralized monitoring of digital status information and system control. SCADA protocols typically implemented in large geographical areas include Ethernet [1].

The Copy Exactly! methodology focuses on matching the manufacturing site to the development site. Matching occurs at all levels for physical inputs and statistically-matched responses (outputs). This process enables continuous matching over time by using coordinated changes, audits, process control systems, and joint fab management structures. Physical inputs such as equipment configuration, chemical purity, facilities, and equipment hookups derive from the same specifications. In-line processes or equipment monitors that predict product performance, yield, or reliability must match at all levels. Originally, the Copy Exactly! procedure was for tool sets and process, but Intel has since encompassed the entire fabrication plant into the strategy model in recent years [2].

ABC Company is a solar energy corporation. ABC company produces solar cells based on inorganic thin film technology, in contrast to Silicon technology developed by most Chinese solar cell corporations, the price competition is not good, strong when thin-screen technology is a new technology that requires mass production and takes time to optimize than a traditional production technology... The company has a production system with automation technology up to 70-80

However, there are still many problems encountered in information management and system monitoring when most machines and lines' monitoring and parameter adjustment operations are manual and semi-manual. The article presents an automatic tracking solution being deployed and developed at the company. Using the available tools and the programming solution to create a system to automatically handle the data collection, solving the problems encountered by manual operation.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Manufacturers face many challenges. Except strong competition from globalization, they need to comply with strict industry regulations, reduce their environmental footprint, meet changing customer behavior and much more. To meet all these conditions and remain competitive, companies must address multiple requirements simultaneously. They must adapt to changing conditions while meeting client expectations. Any deviation from these expectations results in a poor consumer experience and can create an opportunity for customers to move away. Continuously improving machines and factory operations is thus of critical importance to manufacturers. But to quantify improvements, you must be aware of your current machine performance. This is where PLC data logging and condition monitoring kicks in [3].

Businesses often value intellectual property as an asset but forget that their data may be another important industrial

property just waiting to be monetized. Machine data may be one of the most underused and undervalued assets of any organization. This is astonishing if you realize that some of the most important insights you can gain across IT and your business are hidden in that data: it contains a definitive record of all activity and behavior of your machines, peripheral devices, sensors, servers, servo drives, PLCs, HMIs, IP cameras, robots, networks and other industrial equipment, just waiting to be analyzed [3].

The cross-industry standard process for data mining, known as CRISP-DM, is an open standard process model that describes common approaches used by data mining experts. It is the most widely-used analytics model [3]. Machine data can tell you exactly how your machines are performing. It can tell you everything about the cycle time of the machine, malfunctions, downtime, and operating time. In case of breakdowns, the data can reveal where, when and why it went wrong. It also allows you to keep track whether temperature, humidity and gas concentrations are constantly within the normal operating range. It can even reveal answers to more abstract questions, such as, which process variables influence quality and yield, which process variables predict equipment failure or tell you whether product quality, quantity or accuracy meets expectations [3].

In the ABC company's case, there are 3 factory areas with identical designs in terms of processes and machines located in 3 countries with a cost of more than 1 billion dollars in each area, because it is a high-tech field. Copy Exactly! (CE) is a Manufacturer strategy, in that the data must be control and list to document or database... to standardize, and real data will be established according to the normalized study dataset. The term CE was first mentioned by Intel, where CE was implemented to carry out the construction of high-tech manufacturing plants based on a standardized pre-existing process, it made the efficiency of building facilities more efficient. new systems become fast, and at the same time help control new systems become stable quickly.

Required machine parameters are researched and tested at a lab in the US with vendors, researched machine operating parameters when it is confirmed to be stable will be carried out the next step is to build a system. standard parameter system, of that stage (an automatic standard production system is divided into many stages, many system clusters and can have 1 or more production lines), all widths of the machine The hook on each line much be the same, and the same between factories, and the same between sites, and based on that one common standard, that common standard is visually materialized for engineers to follow. Monitor and edit as control Plan file. The control plan is the most important document, and it is imperative to set the same machine parameters, in order to achieve the operating goals, set by the parent company, the parameters can be marked as fixed. or variable (adjustable variable), depending on the setting of that parameter.

After the control plan from the lab is sent to the operating plants, engineers must review and audit it. The current

Figure 1. Process design of system engineering

audit is done manually and causes 2 main types of waste: human idle time. There are stages to record all the current parameters of the machine into a separate file (called a fingerprinting file) that takes up to 3 working days for 1 worker. The need to improve this work is commensurate with the production level and scale of the automated system, as it will become a bottleneck impeding the continuous monitoring process. The solar panel efficiency is one of the most important product's attributes, ABC control it around 18.3%, but that strategic goal always has a large cyclical fluctuation, the drop in solar efficiency can fluctuate up to 0.1%. In principle, if CE is perfectly controlled, i.e. all parameters by 5M+E are set according to sample data studied and tested many times, and without exception, then the output the product and all its related characteristics will be achieved. In Problem Analysis, root reason probably is CE implementation. Because if CE is deployed perfectly, product's parameter will be as the same. CE automation process is considered for development.

III. THEORETICAL BASIS & METHODOLOGY

A. PROCESS OF SYSTEM ENGINEERING

Figure 1 is the application process Systems Engineering is designed, modified, and applied appropriately in research, starting the process with identifying old and new workflows, improving processes and designing new processes. The on-demand functional system used to give the overall picture and data flow is described in the next section.

B. SUPERVISORY CONTROL AND DATA ACQUISITION

The term SCADA stands for Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition. A SCADA system is a common process automation system which is used to gather data from sensors and instruments located at remote sites and to transmit and display this data at a central site for control or monitoring purposes. The collected data is usually viewed on one or more SCADA Host computers located at the central or master site.

A real world SCADA system can monitor and control hundreds to hundreds of thousands of I/O points. A typical Water SCADA application would be to monitor water levels

at various water sources like reservoirs and tanks and when the water level exceeds a preset threshold, activate the system of pumps to move water to tanks with low tank levels.

Common analog signals that SCADA systems monitor and control are levels, temperatures, pressures, flow rate and motor speed. Typical digital signals to monitor and control are level switches, pressure switches, generator status, relays motors.

There is typically another layer of equipment between the remote sensors and instruments and the central computer. This intermediate equipment exists on the remote side and connects to the sensors and field instruments. Sensors typically have digital or analog I/O and these signals are not in a form that can be easily communicated over long distances. The intermediate equipment is used to digitize then packetize the sensor signals so that they can be digitally transmitted via an industrial communications protocol over long distances to the central site.

C. DESIGN COMBINED WITH ORIGINAL SCADA SYSTEM

System design is based on SCADA, using some process on SCADA and then the design solution is detached and becomes a 2nd data stream. The above model is like an embedded system in the parent system, but with a more complex output process in terms of software, since the later stage of the solution, the system is completely isolated from the parent system.

D. PROGRAMMABLE LOGIC CONTROLLER

The PLC can be accurately described as a specialized computer. It differs from a typical home or office computer, however, in that, while it cannot handle anywhere near the same diversity of tasks, it does handle the tasks it CAN do at an exceptionally fast speed. Due to the high-speed process of many automated applications, it is absolutely essential that a PLC processor not get bogged down or slowed in the way a traditional computer can. But a fast processor alone will not complete automation tasks as required – the PLC's ability to handle thousands of I/Os (inputs, outputs and input-outputs) with a single processor is what really defines the product as the "brain" of any plc based automated system [4].

A PLC's most important components are its CPU, its I/O modules, and its rack and power supply. The CPU is the brain of the PLC; it handles the mathematical heavy lifting required to run an automated system at an extreme speed. The I/O modules connect the field inputs (the sensory feedback to the machine) and the outputs (the devices to produce mechanical motion and other actions) to the rack. The rack connects the processor and the I/O modules to pass data between the two; the power supply supplies the energy to do this. As per the diagram above, each scan cycle sees the PLC do internal diagnostic checks, check the inputs, execute the program logic, then update output bits accordingly [4].

Most modern control systems employ a PLC (Programmable Logic Controller) to control motors, pumps, valves, and other equipment used in a process. Computer-based HMI (Human Machine Interface) products provide the means by which process personnel interacts with the PLC control system.

We look at machine data processes to automate the manual data collection and audit process. The current main process goes through an FTTM server before going to the server used to get the key parameter data. Because it is a real-time data server, only key parameters or important metrology and sensor indexes will be considered and created columns because the amount of data is very large. That database is called ODS.

Upgrading the server encountered many obstacles to Global's cost-cutting policy. Therefore, to request global to upgrade the server and expand the data of the machine parameters, it is necessary to perform the demo in a different way and analyze the effectiveness of the demo system first.

E. INGEAR DRIVER

Large corporations to small companies worldwide significantly reduced their software costs by eliminating runtime license fees using INGEAR.NET communication tools and Visual Studio .NET. Unlike OPC, which is a middleware application that presents complex and challenging application development for .NET programmers. INGEAR.NET is an embedded class library that provides a direct communications pipeline to the controller, making it extremely fast and easy to talk to your PLC [11].

NET.LOGIX 7.0 provides a direct communication pipeline from Visual Studio.NET to Allen-Bradley series without OPC servers or RSLinx. Fast, powerful and easy to use runtime-free solution for Allen-Bradley. Using NET.LOGIX, you can create, upload and filter tag lists to your application on the fly. Read and write any size or type of large data blocks, including string types, arrays and user-defined types. Form control linking allows you to automatically update form controls. Unsolicited message support for ControlLogix, CompactLogix, SoftLogix and ControlLogix gateway, MicroLogix 1100, SLC 5/05 and PLC-5E. Usage Procedure:

- Step 1: Add Ingear libraries to a new or existing Visual Studio .NET Project.
- Step 2: Add code to connect to the PLC then begin reading and writing values.
- Step 3: When completed application, deploy, and distribute your program's runtime free.

IV. MODEL SYNTHESIS AND GENERATIVE MODELING

A. CONCEPT OF EMBEDDED SYSTEM

In the initial required functional design, three main functional clusters of a data system were identified, starting from raw data processing, combining processing and database extraction, and then putting the data directly into the database.

Figure 2. Functional Baseline

Figure 3. 0-level Data flow Diagram

develop a tool that supports remote and cross-platform visibility and monitoring as Figure 2.

Large embedded systems consist of many sub-components, including raw data signal processing systems, database processing components, and web components that convert classified and modeled data into information for Engineers. In the first-level data flow model, we can see two main processing and query flows, originating from the PLC and originating from the XML base, and the tag names for querying and parsing are defined in a database. origin, then the actual data tables are combined to form the actual database. Realize this structure through Azure database engine. By further decomposing the Data flow diagram to the next level, we get in more detail the components and subsystems of each thread. The new system is built between the old SCADA structures, in which some old components of the SCADA system need to be standardized, or developed more comprehensively and completely to be able to integrate new processing flows designed.

B. SCOPE OF THIS PAPER

From raw data source, build a program for transfer, binding, modeling and push this to database as Controller connect

Figure 4. 1-level Data flow Diagram (with PLC input)

Figure 5. 1-level Data flow Diagram (with XML input)

method, see figure 6.

These 3 components can be considered as the most important components in the SCADA embedded structure, together with the connection protocols, it builds a real-time system, with an intermediate database, it is capable of The ability to operate independently if SCADA fails in a finite time, it does not block the parent system, and especially the above structure can be standardized for many different production systems.

Figure 6. Scope of development

V. RELATED WORK

Figure 7. Process of development

A. FUZZY MATCHING FOR SEARCHING PARAMETER STEP

The project implementation process is described through a flowchart, the parameter evaluation and comparison step between the CE file and the PLC, to make it easier to imagine we answer 3 questions:

- What parameters can be on the PLC?
- How to audit parameters in the present?
- How to do an automatic audit of that parameter?

Development Process is described as in flowchart in Figure 7. Using the fuzzy search algorithm in the process of finding the Tagname defined in the program, the data about the Tagname that the PLC returns the signal is structured in the form of an XML tree in which the large nodes may contain one or more data nodes. If the data is smaller than level 2 (level 0 is the machine program level), if we consider the name data in the form of logic diagrams in the PLC program, it will result in a much more difficult form of testing. Because the vibration logic of a sensor module or a machine's sensor subsystem is very complex to trace through the path on the sensor diagram, tree name is showing in Figure 11. With n is size of Natural vector, m is size of Metadata vector that is not labelled. In the worst case, Big-O = $O(n \times m)$.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for Fuzzy Attributes Matching

Require: arr_para ; arr_para_meta ; $leaf_node$

Ensure: arr_para_meta

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1: for each  $c \in arr\_para$  do
2:    $c' \leftarrow leaf\_node$ ;  $count \leftarrow 0$ ;  $count\_dec \leftarrow 0$ 
3:    $total\_count = c.name.length$ 
4:   for  $j = 0 \rightarrow c.name.length$  do
5:     for  $k = 0 \rightarrow c'.name.length$  do
6:       Apply ASM
7:       if  $ASMc.name[j] \rightarrow c'.name[k] == 1$ 
      then
8:          $count+ = 1$ 
9:       end if
10:    end for
11:  end for
12:   $weight\_name = \frac{count}{total\_count}$ 
13:  for  $j = 0 \rightarrow c.name.length$  do
14:    for  $k = 0 \rightarrow c'.description.length$  do
15:      Apply ASM
16:      if  $ASMc.name[j] \rightarrow c'.description[k] ==$ 
17:      1 then
18:         $count\_dec+ = 1$ 
19:      end if
20:    end for
21:  end for
22:   $weight\_dec = \frac{count\_dec}{total\_count}$ 
23:  if  $c.value == c'.val$  then
24:     $weight\_val == 1$ 
25:  else
26:     $weight\_val == 0$ 
27:  end if
28:   $weight = \frac{\alpha * weight\_name + \beta * weight\_dec + \gamma + weight\_val}{\alpha + \beta + \gamma}$ 
29:  if  $weight \geq weight\_st$  then
30:     $arr\_para\_meta.push(c')$ 
31:     $arr\_para.pop(c)$ 
32:  end if
33: end for
    
```

In more advanced PLC designs, a more structured programming approach is taken with the use of “tags,” which are stored within the PLC’s memory in a tag database.

With a Tag Database, all function blocks, including contacts, coils, program variables (e.g., as a timer value called “Transmitter_RF_Mute_Timer”), as well all other objects, are stored as variables with attributes such as initial value, float, string, integer, Boolean (on/off), ASCII text, discreet inputs and discreet outputs. While this may seem confusing at first-glance, it’s a superior approach for more complex designs but does require (as in structured programming languages) the designer to declare these variables “tags,” as well as the data type in advance of their use in the program.

One salient features of this design is that all of this information (ladder program, variables and comments) is stored

Figure 8. Data Organization in PLC Program - tree with 4 level

within the PLC, so it's rather self-documenting — that is to say, anyone making modifications can download the entire PLC program into the programming software, even if they do not have access to the original programmer's file. (As you might expect, PLCs can be password-protected.)

Much as in programming languages, you can also assign an initial value to the variable or tag. Data arrays may also be defined in the tag database and in fact, this is how I chose to construct a table of pattern change times for an AM station directional controller with the months as the row data and the pattern change times as the column data.

In summary, Tags are names that you assign to variables of any type stored in the PLC memory. Some examples of tag names might be: Ant_Sw_Delay, RF_Loss_Delay, Overtemp_Alarm_Delay, etc.

Using BFD Algorithm for searching in this data tree, build the algorithm of searching in root level-3 and level-

Figure 10. Processing Time

4(this level has many attribute in root data -> string value matching). In the worst case, with V is a size of data structure vector, Big-O = $O(V^2)$.

Figure 9. PLC Data structure and searching step

B. FUNCTIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Deploy structure of function and prototype, the four main object is: CE file, PLC, Application, CE file out. Summarize, we have built a program structure with the highest functional processing complexity, in the worst case, with n is length of CE list, Big-O = $O(n^2)$.

This comes from basic nested two-loop search constructs, and there are ways we can improve. The processing speeds on a machine are measured as Figure 10.

Then transfer the CE file database into SQL structure database. Control plan data is controlled and required to be tracked by the research department, this data is standardized and requires all to be the same on a common process of factories. This system is derived from the above requirement, when a series of products belonging to the same processes present many differences in performance and quality, one promotes precise control coming from operational parameters, installation of machine, environment, human... based on 5M+E set of criteria.

The search algorithm in the local program of the PLC (using Ingear driver package - Rockwell Automation develop in .NET framework) or XML file is executed in the Window Application, by sending the Tagname and querying the tag value, and then sending it back to the server and the

Figure 11. Function Block with four objects

Figure 12. Database design

Web app to execute the query. The hardware and connection method is developed with TCP/IP method.

VI. CONCLUSION

After running and exporting data and writing some extension functions, the project will be packaged and become a template for the development on other processes.

This is a simple process in the Production process chain, so the project implementation took about 3 months and did not take too long. The output of the project is packaged into a TwinCAT project along with a CE guide file. During future audits, engineers and technicians can easily use the packaged results together with the CE guide file without anyone else's help to automatically record and track information. The number of machines without spending a lot of time and effort moving.

To proceed with adding extensions to the common production process, we repeat from the first step i.e., make a CE file and then get the data and connect.

The application of Fuzzy Attributes Matching is an ideal process of the data science problem of industrial string matching processes.

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